

Transforming Thermoplastic Waste through Manufacturing into Engineering Products

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Acknowledgement

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Outline

- Current landscape of thermoplastic recycling
- Experimental approach
- Implications of the main results to date
- Moving forward

Why focus on PC and PP?

Properties	PC	PP
Chemical structure		
Production volume % out of total thermoplastics [1,2]	2 - 4	16 – 20
% recycled [3]	<10%	<2-5%
Global market size projection [4,5]	\$24.01B in 2025 to \$38.44B by 2030	\$99.3-169.7B in 2025 to \$118.7-219.7B by 2030
Environmental Impact	BPA leaching Low recyclability	GHG emission Landfill toxicity
Degradation time (years)	500 – 1000 in landfills	20 – 30 in landfills

NOTE: About 80% of all consumed plastics are thermoplastics

1. [Plastic Polymers & Resins, Report ID: FBI101583, June 16, 2025](#)
2. [Bulk Chemicals, A01555, August, 2025](#)
3. Houssini, K., Li, J. & Tan, Q. Complexities of the global plastics supply chain revealed in a trade-linked material flow analysis. *Commun Earth Environ* 6, 257 (2025)
4. Global Polycarbonate Market Size, Share, and COVID-19 Impact Analysis, SI1451, January 2023
5. [Polypropylene Market Insights - Size, Share & Industry Forecast 2025 to 2035, June 13, 2025](#)

Major roadblock to recyclability: Quality of feedstock

Polycarbonate Applications [1]

Polypropylene Applications [2]

1. [Polycarbonate market trend](#)
2. [The essential chemistry industry](#)

What recycling methods are being used for PC and PP

- Mechanical recycling
- Chemical recycling

Our project focus:

- In-depth materials research for tailored material compositions for additive manufacturing

Broader aim:

- Increase community access to 3D printing.
- Drive localized and on-demand production.

Questions this research will address

We aim to salvage both PC and PP, regardless of their feedstock or source.

- Is reprocessing affecting the performance of recycled PC and PP?
 - If yes, is degradation occurring and why?
 - Can additives combat this degradation?

Fabrication of test coupons

Barrel (open state) and screws

- Transfer mold (moves melt from barrel to mold)
- Mold (inserted into heater jacket)

Naming Scheme

Parts	
1st	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• r: recycled; or,• v: virgin
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• PC: polycarbonate; or,• PP: polypropylene
2 nd	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• EX: Extrusion
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• 1 (or, 10): Number of melt cycles
3 rd	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• C: Compatibilizer, Polypropylene-graft-maleic anhydride, PP-g-MA; or,• IM: Impact modifier, Poly(ethylene-co-methyl acrylate-co-glycidyl methacrylate)), EMAG; or,• WF: Wood flour mechanical reinforcement
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• 3(or, 5, 10): Weight% of additive in composite

➤ Examples: rPP-EX1-WF10, rPC-EX1-C3-WF10

Tensile behavior of rPC formulations

Tensile behavior of rPC formulations

Theoretical tensile properties of PC: (a) Tensile modulus: 2.2 – 2.5 GPa; (b) Tensile strength: 55 -77 MPa

Flexural behavior of rPC formulations

Theoretical flexural properties of PC: (a) Flexural modulus: 1.8 – 4.1 GPa; (b) Flexural strength: 75 - 110 MPa

Density of rPC composites

Feedstock material:
rPC

Theoretical densities:

- PC: 1.2 g/cm³ [1]
- C: 0.934 g/cm³ [2]
- IM: 0.94 g/cm³ [3]

Thermal transitions of rPC formulations

T_g at 10°C/min

Thermal transition temperatures from literature [1]:

- T_g : 145 – 150 °C
- T_c : 120 – 190 °C
- T_m : 220 – 315 °C

FTIR of rPC

Principal peaks observed in PC:

- 2996 cm^{-1} : C-H single bond stretching, aromatic ring
- 1760 cm^{-1} : C=O carbonate group deformation
- 1500 cm^{-1} : C=C stretching vibration, aromatic ring
- 1200 - 1230 cm^{-1} : O-C-O asymmetric stretching vibration
- 1015 cm^{-1} : O-C-C stretching vibration

Tensile behavior of rPP formulations

Tensile behavior of rPP formulations

Theoretical tensile properties of PP: (a) Tensile modulus: 1.1 – 1.6 GPa; (b) Tensile strength: 27 – 48 MPa

Flexural behavior of rPP formulations

Theoretical flexural properties of PP: (a) Flexural modulus: 0.8 – 1.7 GPa; (b) Flexural strength: 40 - 70 MPa

Impact Behavior

Theoretical impact properties of PC and PP: (a) PP Impact strength: 3 – 30 kJ/m² [1]; (b) PC Impact strength: 10 – 90 kJ/m² [2]

1. [Polypropylene, British plastics federation](#)
2. [Overview of materials for Polycarbonate, extruded, MatWeb material property data](#)

Density of rPP composites

Feedstock material: rPP

Theoretical densities:

- PP: 0.895 – 0.92 g/cm³ [1]
- C: 0.934 g/cm³ [2]

Thermal transitions of rPP formulations

T_m at 10°C/min

T_c at 10°C/min

Theoretical thermal transition temperatures of PP [1,2]:

- T_m : 130 - 170 °C
- T_c : 100 - 120 °C
- T_g : 0 - -20 °C

FTIR of rPP

Principal peaks of Polypropylene

- 2840 – 2950 cm⁻¹: C-H stretching vibration in methyl and methylene groups
- 1455 cm⁻¹: Asymmetric C-H bending in -CH₃
- 1376 cm⁻¹: Symmetric C-H bending in -CH₃

Conclusions and going forward

Is reprocessing affecting the performance of recycled PC and PP?

Both PC and PP formulations withstand 10 melt cycles.

Is degradation occurring, and why?

Extensive degradation not observed.

Can additives combat this degradation

Additives didn't significantly affect our properties, except:

1. Enhanced performance in PP/WF-based formulations
2. Reduction in the tensile modulus of PC.

Moving forward:

- Study PC/PP blends across extrusion temperature, residence time, and reprocessing cycles.
- Conduct detailed rheology analysis of all formulations.
- Introduce reclaimed glass fiber into PP and PC (to combat the tensile modulus reduction).